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Social Factors As Determinants Of Secondary School Students' Risky Sexual Behaviours In Obio/Akpor Local Government Area Of Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

This study examines some social factors as determinants of secondary school students' risky sexual behaviours in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State. The research design was ex-post-facto. Three objectives which were carefully and systematically transformed into research questions and corresponding null hypotheses guided the study. The population of the study was all public senior secondary school students in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area. At the time of the study, there were 14 public secondary schools in the Area. (Source. Post Primary Education Board Obio/Akpo, 2019). In determining the sample for the study, Simple Random Sampling Balloting was used to select 6 secondary schools in the Local Government. 117 students that were involved in risky sexual behaviours were used as sample for the study. Two instruments titled Risky Sexual Behaviour Inventory (R.S.B.I) and Social Factors Questionnaire (S.F.Q) were used as instruments for data collection. The reliability of the instruments was established using Cronbach Alpha method and the coefficients obtained were 0.81 and 0.67 for Risky Sexual Behaviour Inventory and Social Factor Questionnaire respectively. Mean, Standard deviation, t-test and one- way ANOVA were used to answer the research questions and test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The results show that there is significant influence of peer group on students' risky sexual behaviours, risky sexual behaviour is higher in those experiencing peer influence than in those that are not. There is significant influence of family type on students' risky sexual behaviours and there is significant influence of age on student's risky sexual behaviour in Obio-Akpor local government area of Rivers state. Based on the findings, recommendations were made one of which is that parents/caregivers should try as much as possible to know the kind of friends their children keep.

Keywords: Risky sexual behaviour, Sexual transmitted infection, Adolescents, Nuclear family

INTRODUCTION

Macmillan English Dictionary defines sexual as involving or relating to sex, concerning relationships between men and women or the way that people think men and women should behave e.g sexual politics, sexual stereotyping e.t.c, it sees behaviour as the way that someone behaves and defines behave as to do things in a particular way while Ramaligham (2006) defines behaviour as objectively or publicly observable responses. It excludes such conscious phenomena as thinking, perceiving, judgment and the like, except as these may be studied for their consequences. Organisms response to, or interaction with their internal environment brings about covert behaviour. Covert behaviour is that which is not directly observable by organisms or persons around, but can be psychologically perceived only by the organism which is reacting to the internal environment. Typical examples of covert behaviour include beliefs, thinking, emotional feelings (both the positive and negative types), attitudes particularly the cognitive and emotional components, perceptions, and all other internally or psychologically rooted-activities of organisms. Organisms' response to, or interaction with their external environment brings about overt behaviours. Overt behaviour is the activity of the organism which is physical and external, and can be directly observed. E.g talking, laughing, jumping among others (Nwankwo, 2011). However, risky sexual behaviour can be seen as sexual activities or one's orientation towards sex which endangers his/her life. Risky sexual behaviour puts people at risk for sexually transmitted infections (STIs), unplanned pregnancies and being in sexual relationships before being mature enough to know what makes a healthy relationship. Teens and young adult are at risk than adults. Examples of risky sexual behaviours include among others. Unprotected intercourse without male or female condom use. (2) Having multiple sex partners (3) Having a high-risk partner (one who has multiple sex partners or other risk factors.) (4) Sex trade work etc. People may have risky sexual behaviour because they (a) May not understand the concern about STIs and how they are transmitted. (b) May not talk about safer sex practices with sex partners. . (c) May not understand the challenges of unwanted pregnancy etc. (d) May use alcohol and drugs and have sex. Drug and alcohol impair judgement and make unsafe sex more likely. Moreover, substance abuse can cause a loss of control and unhappiness that can lead to poor judgement and may push one towards unhealthy sexual behaviours.

Secondary school students can be teenagers, young adults or adolescents. But for the purpose of this study, adolescents were used. According to (Peretomode, 2007), the term adolescence is used to refer to the period of transition in the life circle of man from childhood to adulthood. It is the bridge between the life of the child and the life of adult, a period that gives the child the time and opportunity to learn to behave as or to become adult. Landies in Peretomode, (2007) sees adolescence as the period "when the individual is in the process of transfer from the dependent, irresponsible age of childhood to the self-reliant, responsible age of adulthood". It is the period from puberty to maturity and begins roughly from about eleven years and last up to eighteen.

In the society, the high level of prostitution, robbery, kidnapping, thuggery, juvenile delinquency could be traceable to lack of social adjustment including our country's high level of insecurity which ranges from militants, boko haram, herds men, bandits, to unknown gun men, It has been observed with keen interest by the researchers that adolescents nowadays lack proper behaviour sexually. Starting from the family, it has been observed that there are poor communications existing between the adolescent and other members of the family. In most situations at home, the adolescent displays juvenile behaviours like disrespects to elders, quarrelling, fighting, watching pornographies as well as sexual experimentations. These have consequently manifested in the church, the school and the society at large. The high rate of bullying in school, lack of respect for school authorities, high level of truancy, not being punctual, high rate of immorality and perverseness are all indicators of lack of proper social adjustment among adolescents.

Social factors are factors that affect or direct our lives, they are facts and experiences that influence individual's personality, attitudes, and lifestyle. These factors include religion affiliation, ethnicity, education, family, friends, economic status, life partner, political affiliation e.t.c. According to

Onukwufor (2014), human beings are social beings, this means that people live in groups and do things along with other people. We as human beings work, play, learn and live together with other people, we sometimes help and hurt each other, cause happiness and success for each other (Onukwufor, 2014). According to Nwankwo (2011), living organisms, particularly animals including human beings respond to or interact with persons and things in their environment.

Human beings are not passive towards social interaction, rather they actively seek for it. For instance, we visit people, make connections, play games, pledge an enduring commitment and decide to have children. According to Weiten, Lloyd, Dunn and Hammer in Onukwufor (2014), people's interpersonal relations contribute to their happiness. In a study by Diener and Saligman in Onukwufor (2014), people who are satisfied with their friendship networks and who are socially active report above average levels of happiness. But for the sake of this study, the social factors to be considered include Peer group, Family types and Age.

Peer group is the social class in which individuals with similar characteristics interact with each other. Through this medium, ideas are formed and shared among each member. According to Igbo (2006), peer group has a lot of controls on the lives of adolescents. In most cases, adolescents form peer association which to a large extent determines how they talk, walk, behave, relate or even what they wear. For instance, individuals who attach themselves to gang may tend to be juvenile in nature resulting to anti-social behaviours such as bullying, fighting, quarrelling, even rapping etc in the way portraying improper social adjustment.

Family is one of the basic grounds for socialization of the child. Parents in the family do well to adopt various means in training of their children. Parents adopt all that constitute parental control. Parental control relates to those methods, techniques, strategies (verbal and non-verbal) which parents may use in raising their children. Parental control could be positive or negative. According to Rosberg (2004), parents with positive controls tend to raise children with higher level of responsibility, while parents with negative controls do not. This sense of responsibility however guides and directs them in creating and maintaining good relationships with people.

The family type in this study include Nuclear, Extended, Single Parent families. Nuclear family is one in which the father, mother and children are the only members of the family and they all live together. In this type of family, children are dependent on their parents for their education and wellbeing. Extended family is one in which distance relations are linked to the unit. These relations include: Aunts, Uncles, Cousins, Nephews and Nieces. In this kind of setting, love is extended or prolonged. Berndth (2007) stated that, the single parent family has been one of the fastest growing types in most parts of the world. Single parent family has come into existence as a result of divorce, dissolution, death, separation and out of wed-luck birth. Children from such families may suffer from guilt and loneliness, feelings of anger, unsatisfied parental care e.t.c. Young ones in single parent families contend with intense emotions due to their parents' abrupt departure or death. For many adolescents, the absence of one of the parents seem to have profound negative effect on them. Under this type of family, problem arises because children at adolescence stage of development are expected to be under authority, to be carefully monitored, and we also know that in this type of family monitoring is inadequate, the children suffer from a number of behavioural disorders (Berndth, 2007).

Age can be seen as a specific relatively time limited stage of the individual's mental development and moulding of one's personality (Ramalingham, 2006). It is the number of years that someone has lived or existed.

The aim of the study was to examine factors determining secondary school students' risky sexual behaviours in Obio/Akpo Local Government Area of Rivers State. In clear terms, the study intended to:

1. discover the difference between the influence of students experiencing peer influence and those not experiencing on risky sexual behaviours in Obio- Akpor LGA of Rivers state.
2. ascertain the influence of family types on risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students in Obio-Akpor LGA of Rivers state

3. find out the influence of age on risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students in Obio-Akpor LGA of Rivers state

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the difference between the influence of students experiencing peer influence and those not experiencing on risky sexual behaviours in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State?
2. What is the influence of family types on risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students in Obio/Akpo Local Government Area of Rivers State?
3. What is the influence of age on risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students in Obio/Akpo Local Government Area of Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance were formulated to guide the study.

1. There is no significant difference between the influence of students experiencing peer influence and those not experiencing on risky sexual behaviours in Obio/Akpo Local Government Area of Rivers State.
2. There is no significant difference in the influence of family types on secondary school students' risky sexual behaviours in Obio/Akpo Local Government Area of Rivers State
3. There is no significant difference in the influence of the various age groups on secondary school students' risky sexual behaviours in Obio/Akpo Local Government Area of Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

The research design adopted for the study was ex-post-facto. According to Nwankwo (2010), it involves collecting and analyzing data about some variables retrospectively or about variables which are already in place without manipulating any of them, in order to find out how some of them influence, or are related to other variables. The design was used because the variables already exist, and researchers measure the extent to which peer group, family types and age influence secondary school students' risky sexual behaviours. The population of the study comprised of all students in public senior secondary schools in Obio/Akpo Local Government Area of Rivers State. At the time of the study, there were 14 public secondary schools in the Area. (Rivers State Ministry of Education).

In determining the sample for the study, Simple Random sampling balloting was used to select 6 secondary schools in the Local Government. The sample size for the study was 117. Two instruments were used for the study. The Risky Sexual Behaviour Inventory (RSBI) developed by the researchers and The Social Factor Questionnaire (SFQ) developed by the researchers. The risky sexual behaviour inventory contained 15 items. The social factor questionnaire had two sections, A & B. Section A captured demographic data including family types and age, while section B had 10 items that measured peer group influence. In order to determine students that are experiencing peer influence and those not experiencing peer influence, the researchers considered the 10 item scale. The maximum score being 40 and the minimum being 10. The researchers set a cut off score of 20 by dividing the scale into two. Those students who scored 20 and above were considered to be experiencing peer influence while those who scored less were considered not to have peer influence. At the end, 72 students were identified as being influenced by peers while 45 had no such influence. The items were rated on a 4 point scale of, Strongly Agreed (4 points), Agree (3 points), Disagree (2 points), Strongly Disagree (1 point) for risky sexual behaviour and peer group influence.

To ensure face and content validity of the instruments, the researchers gave copies of the instruments to their supervisors and two other experts in the department of Educational Psychology, Guidance and Counselling. They determined whether the items contained in the instruments were adequate enough for the study. Also they ensured that the items measured what they are intended to measure. Language

difficulty level was also ensured so as to make sure that it is neither too high nor too low for the population being studied.

The reliability of the instruments was determined through Cronbach's Alpha method. The Risky Sexual Behaviour Inventory had a reliability coefficient of 0.81 while the Social Factor Questionnaire (peer group) had a reliability coefficient of 0.67. The coefficients so obtained were high enough for the use of the instruments as reliable for the study. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while null hypotheses were tested using t-test and one-way ANOVA at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Research Question 1: *What is the difference between the influence of students experiencing peer influence and those not experiencing on risky sexual behaviours in Obio/Akpo Local Government Area of Rivers State?*

Hypothesis one: There is no significant difference between the influence of students experiencing peer influence and those not experiencing on risky sexual behaviours in Obio/Akpo Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Table 4.1: Shows t-test analysis of the influence of peer group on students' risky sexual behaviours.

Peer influence	N	\bar{X}	SD	t	df	α	Sig.	Result
Experiencing peer influence	72	47.85	6.44					
Not experiencing peer influence	45	35.44	12.98			0.05		
				6.87	115		0.000	Significant (Reject Ho)

The analysis in table 4.1 shows that students who were influenced by their peers were 72 while those that are not influenced were 45. Their mean and standard deviation values were 47.85, 6.44 and 35.44, 12.98 respectively. From their mean values, it is shown that the level of risky sexual behaviour among those experiencing peer influence is higher compared to those who are not. Calculated t value was 6.87 while sig. Value was 0.00. Therefore, since sig.(P=0.000 < 0.05) is less than 0.05 alpha at 115 degree of freedom, the null hypothesis is rejected meaning that there is a significant difference in the influence of peer group on risky sexual behaviours of adolescents in secondary schools in Obio/Akpo Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Research Question 2: What is the influence of family types on risky sexual behaviour among secondary school students in Obio/Akpo Local Government Area of Rivers State?

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference in the influence of family types on secondary school students' sexual behaviours in Obio/Akpo Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Table 4.2 Shows mean (\bar{X}), standard deviation (SD) and one-way ANOVA of influence of family types on adolescents risky sexual behaviours.

Family types	N	\bar{X}	SD				
Nuclear	72	35.13	4.46				
Extended	30	31.17	4.48				
Single parent	15	30.80	1.61				
ANOVA							
	Sum of sq.	df	Ms.F	Alpha	sig	Result	
Between group	462.45	2	231.22				Significant
Within group	2040.44	114	17.89	12.92	0.05	0.001	(Reject)
Total	2502.89	116					

Table 4.2 shows that adolescents identified with nuclear, extended and single parent families were 72, 30 and 15 respectively. Their means values on risky sexual behaviours were 35.13, 31.17 and 30.80. These means show that nuclear family pattern produced highest level of risky sexual behaviours among adolescents. ANOVA table shows F value of 12.92 while sig value is 0.001. Hence, since the sig ($p=0.001<0.05$) is less than 0.05 alpha level, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is significant difference in the influence of nuclear, extended and single parent family type on secondary school students' risky sexual behaviours in Obio/Akpo Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Research Question 3: What is the influence of age on risky sexual behaviours among secondary school students in Obio/Akpo Local Government Area of Rivers State?

Hypothesis Three: There is no significant difference in the influence of the various age groups on secondary school students' sexual behaviours in Obio/Akpo Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Table 4.3 shows one-way ANOVA of influence of age on adolescents risky sexual behaviour.

Age	N	\bar{X}	SD				
10-13	22	37.32	5.88				
14-16	66	33.41	4.22				
17-19	29	31.17	2.42				
ANOVA							
	Sum of sq.	df	Ms.	F	Alpha	sig	Result
Between group	477.44	2	238.72				significant
Within group	2050.87	114	17.99	13.27	0.05	0.001	(Reject)
Total	2528.31	116					

Table 4.3 shows that adolescents identified within the age range of 10-13, 14-16 and 17-19 were 22, 66 and 29 respectively. Their means values were 37.32, 33.41 and 31.17. This means that age 10-13 years had adolescents with highest level of risky sexual behaviours. ANOVA table shows F value to be 13.27 while sig value is 0.000. Hence, since the sig ($p=0.000<0.05$) is less than 0.05 alpha level, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is significant difference in the influence of the various age groups on secondary school students' risky sexual behaviours in Obio/Akpo Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Summary of Findings

Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were reached:

1. There was significant influence between students experiencing peer influence and those that are not on risky sexual behaviours in Obio/Akpo L.G.A of Rivers State.
2. Research finding two shows that family type has significant influence on Adolescents risky sexual behaviours, with nuclear family having the highest mean score.
3. There is significant influence of various age groups on Adolescents risky sexual behaviours, with age 10-13 years having the highest mean score.

DISCUSSIONS OF FINDINGS

From finding one, it is revealed that there was significant difference between the influence of students experiencing peer influence and those that are not on risky sexual behaviours in Obio/Akpo L.G.A of Rivers State. Those experiencing peer influence were 72, their mean and standard deviation values were 47.85 and 6.44 while those that are not experiencing peer influence were 35.44 and 12.98. By that, it shows that the risky sexual behaviour is high in those experiencing peer influence. These findings mean that the type of company an individual keeps can determine if he or she will engage in risky sexual behaviour or not. For instance, if adolescents attached to company of friends that engage in illicit sexual behaviour, such adolescents may likely engage in same behaviour. This finding may come because majority of adolescents have built their lives around conformity to peer group. Also it could be that the respondents are totally in agreement with the age long adage that says “birds of the same feather flock together”. The finding is not so surprising to the researchers because they are aware that peer influence has major impact on the lives and decision of adolescents. From various research findings, it is also revealed that peer influence significantly determines the behaviour of Adolescents. This finding is in line with that reported by Ugo (2015) who stated that peer pressure has significant relationship with sexual attachments of students in secondary schools.

Furthermore, research finding two shows that there is a significant difference in the influence of family types on risky sexual behaviour. This result means that adolescents will either engage or disengage in risky sexual behaviour depending on the type of family they come from. For instance, the mean values have shown that adolescents from nuclear families had the highest mean value on risky sexual behaviours. This finding somehow is surprising to the researchers because to the best of their knowledge, nuclear family should provide the best training for the adolescent due to the presence of father and mother. They should be able to curb the excesses of their children. This finding also may come because most parents do not take care of their children any more. They are too busy or neglectful in their parental responsibilities. The finding is how ever in support of that reported earlier by Bernard (2012) who stated that family background significantly influence the sexual behaviour of students.

Finally, finding three shows that there is a significant difference between the various age groups on their influences on risky sexual behaviours among adolescents. This means that the adolescents engage in risky sexual behaviours depending on their ages. For instance, Adolescents of age group of 10-13 obtained the highest mean scores on risky sexual behaviour. This result may mean that since this category of adolescents are not advanced and probably not too matured in age, they may not fully understand the risk involved in engaging in sexual behaviour. On the other hand, it could be that this category of adolescents are simply trying to explore the teenage years. This finding is actually surprising to see younger adolescents engage more in risky sexual behaviour. However, the finding of Mark (2011) showed no difference in the influence of age group on sexual behaviours of students.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. Since the finding of the study indicates that peer group has significant influence on Adolescents risky sexual behaviours, parents/care givers should try as much as possible to know the kind of friends their children keep.
2. The discovery of this study reveals that family type has significant influence on Adolescents risky sexual behaviours. It is therefore recommended that parents should be very close and happy as well as extending warmth to their Adolescent children to reduce the incidence of risky sexual behaviours among Adolescents.
3. It is also recommended that students should undergo counselling concerning their sexual behaviour. The counselling process should be modified according to their age.

REFERENCES

- Aibinu, I. O (2018). *Socio-Cultural and environmental factors as predictors of women and children trafficking in Lagos and Edo States, Nigeria*. Unpublished doctoral thesis, University of Ibadan.
- Akpama, S. I (2008). *Socio-economic factors as predictors of sexual abuse of adolescents in selected secondary schools in Akwa Ibom and Cross River States, Nigeria*. Unpublished doctoral thesis, University of Ibadan.
- Baltus, R.K (2012). *Personal psychology for life and work*. New York: MC Graw-Hill.
- Barber, B.K (2012). *Marital quality, parental behaviours and adolescent self esteem*. In B.K Barber & B.C Rollings (Ed), *parent-adolescent Interaction* (pp.49-74) Lanham, MD
- Bernard, G.N (2012). *Family background and location as one of the social factors influencing sexual behaviour of students in Anambra State, Nigeria*. Unpublished master dissertation. Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka.
- Igbo, E. O (2006). Marital trajectories and mental health. *Journal of Health and Social Behaviour* (41/5) 451-464.
- Michael, R. (2007). *Macmillan English Dictionary* second edition A& C Black publishers Ltd.
- Olds, S.W & Papalia, D.E (2011). *Human developments* (7 edition) New York: MC Graw-Hill.
- Rosberg, I (2004). *Defence of single- parent families*. New York University Press.
- Steinberg, L (2011). *Adolescence* (9 edition) Illinois: MC Graw-hill.
- Ugo, H.C. (2015). *The influence of social factors on sexual attachment of students in secondary schools in Enugu and Benue States, Nigeria*. Unpublished doctoral Thesis, University of Nigeria, Nsukka.